

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added Course 2020-21 academic year for BPT

YOGA

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added course
on
YOGA
for BPT 2018 batch

Course duration
10 weeks (40 hours)

Course Objectives

1. To provide the necessary knowledge of practice of yoga so that the students learn to practice and also to teach yoga to all age groups for promoting their health and effectiveness.
2. To provide the necessary knowledge and skills of performing Asanas, Mudras, Bandas, Pranayama and meditative postures.

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Course period	From October 2020 till December 2020 (online), during 5 th semester (10 weeks)
Duration	40 hours (4 hours/week)
Language of instruction	English
Participants	BPT 3 rd year undergraduates (2018 batch)

Course Objectives:

1. To provide the necessary knowledge of the theory and practice of yoga so that the students learn to practice and also to teach yoga to all age groups for promoting their health and effectiveness.
2. To provide the necessary knowledge of Asanas, Mudras, Bandas, Pranayama and meditative postures.

COURSE OUTLINE		
MOD	TOPIC	HOURS
1	Introduction: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Yoga philosophy, origin of Yoga, principles and importance of yoga.• Basic yogic principles: Stages of yoga.• Types of yoga: Hatha Yoga, Raja Yoga, Laya Yoga, Bhakti Yoga, Ashtanga Yoga, Karma Yoga.	3
2	Effects of yoga on various systems: Musculoskeletal, Neuro, Cardiovascular, metabolic, Gastrointestinal, mental and reproductive systems.	4
3	Yoga Asana: Principles, muscle work and kinematics; Relevance of asana to exercise. Types of asana: <ol style="list-style-type: none">Forward Bending Asanas: Uttanasana, Padahasthasana, Prasarirapaduttanasana, Janusirsasana, Triangamukhiekapadapaschimottanasana, Paschimottanasana, Ardhapadmabaddapaschimottanasana.Back Bending Asanas: Salabhasana, Bhujangasana, Ustrasana, Dhanurasana, Urdhavadhanurasana, Chakrasana.Standing Asanas: Suryanamaskar, Utkatasana, Urdhvahasthasana, Urdhvhadhanguliasana, Prasarirapadahasthasana, Trikonasana, Parsavakonasana, Ardhashchandrasana, Adhomukhasavanasana, Veerabhadrasana.Inversions: Sirsasana, Sarvangasana, Halasana.Twisting Asanas: Floor twisting, Chair twisting, Standing twisting.Sitting Asanas: Sukhasana, Bhaddakonasana, Padmasana, Ardhapadmasana, Veerasana, Dandasana, Upavistakonasana.Supine Asanas: Suptapadangusthasana, Sukhsamvyayamas.Restorative Asanas: Suptaveerasana, Suptabhaddakonasana, Setubandhasarvangasana, SavasanaTratakas: Visual Training Asanas	25
4	Pranayama, Bandhas and Mudras: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Pranayama definition, phases, types and principles (Ujjai Pranayama, Anulomvilom, Bhastrika, Bhramri, Nadishodhan, Kapalbharti, Omkar, Suryabhedana, Chandrabhedana).• Difference between pranayama and deep breathing.• Meaning of Bandhas and mudras, physical effects, types.	5
5	Dhyana: Meaning and benefits of Dhyana; Intellectual concentration vs dhyana.	3

References:

1. Sri G Dayanidi & Smt. Reena Dayanidy. Principles and methods of yoga practices. ICYER.

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CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This is to certify that

ADHARSH KS (5SU18PT002)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
Assistant Professor
Course Instructor

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean
College of Physiotherapy

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This is to certify that

AISHWARYA N M (5SU18PT004)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

AMRITHA K (5SU18PT007)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

ANAGHA K (5SU18PT008)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
Assistant Professor
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This is to certify that

ANASWARA PURUSHOTHAMAN (5SU18PT009)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

ANJALI MURALEEDHARAN (5SU18PT010)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

ARCHANA A S (5SU18PT011)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

ASHIFA K A (5SU18PT012)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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ASHWAJAKSHI (5SU18PT013)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

AVINASH KUMAR (5SU18PT014)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

BLESSY MOL T T (5SU18PT015)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

BORKAR AMISHA VITTHAL (5SU18PT016)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

BRAHMECHA TANVI NARESH (5SU18PT017)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

BRUNDA N M (5SU18PT018)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

CHACKO PRITY PHILIP (5SU18PT019)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

CIRIL P BABY (5SU18PT020)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

DONA N JESLIN (5SU18PT021)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

FATHIMA THANWEENA (5SU18PT022)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

GOPIKA NANDAN N R (5SU18PT024)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

KADAM TRUPTI RAVINDRA (5SU18PT027)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

MIDHUN YADUBALAN (5SU18PT030)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

MUHAMMED ASHRAF (5SU18PT032)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

MUSSAMMIL ABDULLA (5SU18PT033)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
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Total Hours- 40

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This is to certify that

NAJIL HASHAL A K (5SU18PT034)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
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Total Hours- 40

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This is to certify that

NEHA P K (5SU18PT036)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
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Total Hours- 40

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This is to certify that

PRATHEEKSHA (5SU18PT037)

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Total Hours- 40

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This is to certify that

RAMYA (5SU18PT039)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
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This is to certify that

SALVI AASTHA TUSHAR (5SU18PT041)

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This is to certify that

SHETTIGAR SUNIL VENKATESH (5SU18PT042)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
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Total Hours- 40

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This is to certify that

SHETTY SAKSHI SHEKHAR (5SU18PT043)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
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Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

SHETTY SHRAJAL PRABHAKAR (5SU18PT044)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
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Total Hours- 40

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This is to certify that

SHREYA D S (5SU18PT046)

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Total Hours- 40

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This is to certify that

STEEPHAN VARGHESE (5SU18PT047)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
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Total Hours- 40

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This is to certify that

SWATHIKA B R (5SU18PT049)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

TAMATTA SHANTI CHANDU (5SU18PT050)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

WAGHMODE RUCHITA SANJAY (5SU18PT051)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from October to December 2020 (virtual)

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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